

Traditional Uses of Medicinal Plants in Treating Bone fracture, Urine stone, Stomachache and Jaundice in Chandgad Tahsil (District Kolhapur) of Maharashtra, India

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Abstract An ethnomedicinal survey was under taken to collect information from local rural people about the use of medicinal plants in Chandgad Tahsil. The present paper documents the traditional knowledge of medicinal plant species used to cure Bone fracture, Urine stone and Jaundice. Ethnomedicinal information of medicinal plants was taken from different localities of Chandgad Tahsil by interview with local rural practioners (vaidya). The knowledge about the medicinal plant has been transmitted orally from generation to generation. The people in the study area still have a strong belief in the efficacy and success of hearbal medicine. The present investigation revealed that there are about 5 species of plants used to treat Bone fracture, 9 species of plants used to cure Urine stone, 5 species of plants used to cure stomachache and 5 species of plants used to cure Jaundice. The traditional knowledge of medicinal plants has great potential for research and the discovery of new drugs.

Keywords: Traditional, medicinal plant, Bone fracture, Urine stone, Jaundice. Chandgad Tahsil

Introduction

India is considered to be a store house of medicinal plants. It harbors over 2000 medicinal plant species. During last few decades there has been an increase in the study of medicinal plants and their traditional uses in different parts of the world. Herbal remedies are considered the oldest form of health care known to mankind on this earth. Chandgad Tahsil has a valuable heritage of herbal remedies. The climate of the area is healthy and favorable for growth and development of plants. So area shows rich biodiversity. Many villages of Chandgad tahasil of Kolhapur district are located in the forest area and are far away from city. Its rural people living in remote forests are still depending on the local plant resources for medical treatment. The local rural herbalist or medicine man (health practitioner) called Vaidu. Vaidu cure various diseases of rural people using medicinal plants. Traditionally this treasure of knowledge has been transmitted orally from generation to generation without any written document. With an errosion of traditional culture of tribal and rural peoples invaluable knowledge of medicinal plants is threatened. It is an urgent need to collect and conserve all ethnobotanical information from various communities.

Material and Methods

For gathering information regarding plants used medicinally by the rural vaidus several field trips were undertaken in the villages of chandgad tahsil in different seasons. Ethnobotanical data were collected according to

the methodology suggested by Jain. The ethnobotanical data (local name, mode of preparation, medicinal uses) were collected through questionaries, interviews and discussion among the rural practitioners (vaidu) in their local language and recorded in field note book. The collected information was cross checked with the help of available literature. The specimens were collected from the field and identified with the help of local flora. Names of all key informants were noted and are available on request. The study involved an extensive literature search and herbarium examination.

Observations

Folklore medicinal plants are arranged disease wise with their botanical name, family, local name, part used and mode of administration in table 1.

Result and Conclusion

Present investigation revealed that 9 plant species are used for treatment of Urine stone, 6 plant species are used for treatment of Bone fracture, 5 species of plants used to cure stomachache and 5 plant species are used for treatment of Jaundice. This indicates that rural people of this region possess good knowledge of herbal drugs but their continuous and progressive exposure to modernization may result in extinction of the rich heritage of knowledge in course of time. The part of the plant most used for medicinal purposes were leaves followed by stem bark, roots, fruits, and seeds. Ethnomedicinal data may provide a base to start the search for new compounds related to photochemistry, pharmacognosy and

pharmacology. This may provide new source of herbal drugs and help to understand the molecular basis of their activities. Moreover it may further be mentioned that over exploitation of these species in the name of medicine may

lead some species ultimately to the disappearance in future. Therefore attention should also be made on exploitation and proper utilization of these medicinal plants.

Table 1: List of Medicinal Plants with Botanical Name, Family, Local name, Part used and Administration

Sr. No.	Botanical name, Family and Local name	Part used	Administration
Urine Stone			
1	<i>Bridelia squamosa</i> (Lam.) Gehrm. Euphorbiaceae; Ragat Asan	Bark	One cup bark extract given by empty stomach for seven days.
2	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L. Amaranthaceae; Kurdu	Root	One cup root decoction given for seven days.
3	<i>Cipadessa baccifera</i> (Roth) Miq. Meliaceae ; Narang	Leaf	One cup leaf extract and half cup of milk added with half spoon poppy seed powder taken internally by empty stomach for seven days.
4	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Poaceae; Harali, Durva	Leaf	Whole plant extract taken orally for ten days.
5	<i>Dendrophthoe falcate</i> (L.F.) Loranthaceae; Bandgul, Bande	Leaf	One cup leaf extract taken orally for five days.
6	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> (Buch.-Ham.) Apocynaceae; Pandhara Kuda	Bark	Two spoon bark powder with water given early morning for seven days.
7	<i>Hygrophila schulli</i> (Buch-Ham.) Acanthaceae; Kolshinda	Leaf	One cup leaf extract given with coconut milk.
8	<i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i> (Lamk.) Crassulaceae; Paanphuti	Leaf and Root	Leaf and root extract taken early morning for five days.
9	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L. Asteraceae; Dagadipala, Kunticha pala	Leaf	Leaf extract given early morning for five days.
Jaundice			
1	<i>Achyranthus aspera</i> L. Amaranthaceae; Aghada	Leaf	Two tea spoon leaf juice given for seven days.
2	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb. Lecythidaceae; Kumbha	Bark	Bark juice applied over all body for five days.
3	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L. Euphorbiaceae; Erand	Leaf	One glass leaf extract given orally by empty stomach for five days.
4	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L. Solanaceae; Kamuni	Leaf	Leaf juice given for seven days.
5	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (willd.) Menispermaceae; Amrut vel	Leaf	One cup leaf extract with one spoon honey given early morning for one week.
Bone fracture			
1	<i>Allophyllus cobbe</i> (L.) Sapindaceae; Tipani /Hadsandhi	Leaf	Leaf paste plastered over bone fracture.
2	<i>Casearia championii</i> Thw. Flacourtiaceae; Modi, Hadmodi	Leaf	One glass leaf extract taken internally twice a day for one week and leaf paste applied over fractured part.
3	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb. Lecythidaceae; Kumbha	Bark	Fractured bones of childrens were tightly bound by elongated bark.
4	<i>Pavetta Crassicaillis</i> Bremek Rubiaceae; Papat	Leaf and bark	Leaf paste bind over fractured part for 15 days and one spoon bark powder eaten with coconut kernel for 15 days.
5	<i>Persea macrantha</i> (Nees) Lauraceae; Pulas	Bark	Crushed bark plastered over fractured bone and bark juice given orally.
6	<i>Wendlandia thyrsoides</i> (R. & S.)	Leaf	Leaf paste applied over fractured bones.

	Rubiaceae; Ranper, Tarangi		
Stomachache			
1	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.F.) Mimosaceae; Khair	Bark	Bark decoction taken internally twice a day.
2	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) Apocynaceae; Satvin, Saptaprni	Bark	Bark extract given for ten days.
3	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L. Amaranthaceae; Kate-Mat	Leaf	Leaf paste along with lemon juice taken orally.
4	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Euphorbiaceae; Shendri	Fruit	Fruit cover powder taken internally with water.
5	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.) Rutaceae; Jangli mirachi	Leaf	One cup leaf decoction taken internally.

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